

“EXAMINATION OF THE CHEMICAL MECHANISMS DURING THERMAL TREATMENT OF CARBON FIBER PAN PRECURSORS”

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ABSTRACT

Although not fully understood, the prevailing literature opinion is, that radical processes make a major contribution during thermal stabilization of carbon fiber PAN (polyacrylonitrile) precursors and are even the only mechanisms to occur in homopolymers under inert conditions, forming a continuous ladder structure. However, the facts, that a) the origin of these radicals remains unknown and b) the radicals introduced during the PAN synthesis do not induce any cyclization reactions, casted some doubt on this mechanism in our view. Therefore various thermal and spectroscopic experiments on PAN homopolymers with differently deuterated sites and novelly synthesized corresponding oligomers, containing several Acrylonitrile repeating units, have been conducted in this present work, to further evaluate the ongoing mechanisms during the thermal stabilization processes. Besides that, chemical agents were added to polymer and oligomer samples and their influences on the thermal behaviour have been investigated by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). The mentioned various isotopically labelled compounds have been synthesized and used as single components or in mixtures, in DSC-experiments, to distinguish inter- from intramolecular pathways by this method. The results suggest a participation of all three hydrogens in one PAN-repeating unit during the stabilization process under inert conditions and a clear intermolecular dependency. Our results strongly indicate that the so far proposed solely radical intramolecular mechanism cannot be the major process under inert conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their unique combination of various properties, carbon fibers have attracted a rising interest in industry and academia over the last decades. These properties include high tensile strengths and elastic modulus at low densities, combined with high creep resistances and an inert behaviour towards many chemical agents.¹ Therefore their use in lightweight compound materials (often referred to as carbon fibers-reinforced polymers, CFRP), ranging from automotive over sports-gear to windmill manufacturing, are highly desired.

At the early stages of the CFRP production, fibers have usually been based on pitch or textile rayon as precursor materials. With the market and the number of applications for carbon-fibers/resin compound materials steadily increasing, the resulting properties of such materials need to be tailored to certain demands. For those needs, the introduction of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based carbon fibers precursors has been favourable where small amounts of certain comonomers are added to improve the performance³. PAN based carbon fibers (CF) generally show higher tensile strengths, better processibility and a better carbon yield than the above mentioned precursors, which makes them the only candidates at the moment for high performance fibers.²

To obtain carbon fibers from PAN, three general manufacturing steps have to be performed: The woven PAN fibers are stabilized under an air atmosphere between 200-300° C firstly. This stabilization results in non-meltable and non-flammable pre-stabilized PAN fibers, which are further carbonized and then graphitized under an inert atmosphere at temperatures up to 3000 °C eventually. Depending on the temperatures and other process parameters, properties like tensile-strength or the elastic modulus can be varied over a wide range³.

In spite of intensive work on the analysis of the stabilization step dating back to the 1950s⁴ and resulting in numerous publications^{5, 6, 7, 8, 9}, the chemical mechanism is by no means understood and several different reaction pathways for the stabilization process have been suggested so far. The complete process can be sub-divided in two competitive reaction channels, one entirely thermally driven and one dependent on dioxygen as reaction partner, where both channels are not occurring independently of each other.

In this contribution we concentrate on the entirely thermally driven pathway working under inert conditions and also excluding the influence of comonomers by using PAN-homopolymer as precursor material.

By now, a radically induced intramolecular ladder-structure forming cyclization mechanism, firstly proposed by Kim et al.¹⁰, is suggested to occur as main process under these conditions in several papers. Also, the initiation of the ladder-structure formation via Thorpe-Ziegler-analogous azomethine cyclization was proposed. For the latter an intermolecular pathway was also taken into account leading to crosslinking between the chains (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Possible reaction pathways during the thermal stabilization of polyacrylonitriles

We have performed mechanistic studies on the stabilization step that open up new points of view on the afore-mentioned assumptions and will help to clarify further the complex process.

On this purpose we have synthesized a series of PAN homopolymers via free radical polymerization varying the degree of polymerization (DOP between 60 and 350) and the deuterium labelling (d_0 , d_1 and d_3). Also we synthesized defined oligomers such as the trimer by means of multi-step organic synthesis and examined them under inert thermal conditions to mimic the stabilization step in a more controlled manner.

Questions to be addressed are

- Does the degree of polymerization play an important role in this process?
- Can an intramolecular radically induced ladder-structure formation be supported?
- Are intermolecular reactions decisive?
- Is the contribution of a Thorpe-Ziegler-type reaction likely?

2. Experimental

Non-deuterated acrylonitrile (d_0 -AN) and d_3 -AN were commercially purchased as reagent grade with monomethylether hydroquinone added as a polymerization inhibitor and removed from this and degassed via condensation. d_1 -AN was synthesized according to the procedure published by Leitch.¹¹ DMF, as a polymerization solvent, d_0 -AN, d_1 -AN and d_3 -AN were dried, degassed and stored under Argon. THF and diethyl ether have been dried using a two-column Grubbs purification system. Any other reagents were used without further purification unless otherwise noted.

Experimental data were obtained from the following instruments: NMR/Oxford Instruments NMR AS 400, IR/Thermo Nicolet Nexus 470, DSC/NETZSCH DSC204F1

Methacrylonitrile was synthesized from a mixture of commercial methacrylamide (Sigma-Aldrich, 98%) with P_4O_{10} , which was heated up to 190 °C under a slight vacuum. 1H -NMR pure methacrylonitrile could be collected in a cooling trap in 70% yield.

Polymerization of the d_0 -, d_1 - and d_3 -PAN homopolymers have been executed according to the following procedure, only varying in the corresponding mass of monomers added (see Table 1):

25 mg of the initiator (Azo-bis-(isobutyronitril), AIBN) were dissolved in 5 ml of DMF under Argon in a Glovebox. To the sealed flask, the corresponding amounts of the monomers were added through a septum. These solutions were stirred with 500 rpm at 65 °C for 24 hours. The reactions were quenched with 100 mg of $CuCl_2$ in 5 ml H_2O . The precipitates were collected, have been washed several times with water and methanol and dried for 10 hours under vacuum at 60 °C. The products were white, sometimes pale yellowish solids with yields between 84-98%. They were characterized via NMR- and IR-spectroscopy and elemental analysis and used for further experiments like that.

DSC measurements were carried out in 5 pin-holed Aluminium crucibles with a heating rate of 20K/min unless pointed out otherwise. The experimental data have been evaluated with the NETZSCH Proteus – Thermal Analysis software (Version 6.1.0)

Synthesis of 2,4,6-Triscyano-4-(t-butylacetate)-heptane (I), i) in Figure 6: 1ml of t-butylcyanoacetate (1eq) was dissolved in 15 ml of t-butanol. 20 mg NaH (0.83 mmol, 15mol%) were added under Argon. After gas evolution stopped, 1.2 ml (2eq) of freshly distilled methacrylonitrile were added. The mixture was heated under Argon at 80 °C for 48h. Afterwards the volatiles have been removed and 1 ml H_2O was added. This was extracted with an overall 100 ml of Et_2O (three times). The organic phase was dried and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. A colorless oil was obtained. Recrystallization from Et_2O gave 1.7g of a white solid (Yield: 87%).

Synthesis of 2,4,6-Triscyanoheptane (II), ii) in Figure 6: 900 mg (3,26 mmol) of **I** were heated under Argon for 20 min at 180 °C. After cooling to room temperature, the residue was recrystallized from Et_2O /EtOH to obtain 550 mg of white crystals (3.14 mmol, Yield:90 %).

Cyclization of II, see Figure 7: 110 mg (0,63 mmol, 1eq) of **II** were dissolved in 30 ml dry THF. This solution was cooled to -30 °C in an i-Propanol/liquid air-bath for 15 min. Afterwards 0.32 ml of a 2m-solution of lithiumdiisopropylamide in THF (0.63 mmol, 1eq) was added dropwise. After the addition was finished the slightly yellow solution was warmed slowly to RT and left stirring over night. The volatiles have been removed and 1 ml H_2O was added. This was extracted with Et_2O (100ml, three times) and the organic layer was dried and the solvent evaporated. The residue was recrystallized from Et_2O to obtain 100 mg (Yield: 82%) of pale yellow crystals.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Influence of the degree of polymerization

The determination of the molecular weight distribution and the averaged degree of polymerization of PAN homopolymer is not a trivial task.

SEC measurement was performed by us (these measurements were performed by Dr. Felix Scheliga, University of Hamburg) but since PAN standard samples are not easily available, these values were determined against a polystyrene standard. A correction via Mark-Houwink equation was done, and, because it was doubted in the literature that this correction is justified in the case of PAN,

we double-checked the averaged degree of polymerization by means of end group analysis via ¹H NMR spectroscopy. For this evaluation an assumption must be made according to the termination reaction of the polymerization. The ¹H NMR spectra did not contain any traces of signals in the olefinic region and thus a complete termination by means of recombination was assumed. This is in accordance with what is expected for the free radical polymerization of acrylonitrile. The polydispersity of the molecular weight distribution was found to be between 1.5-2.0 (expected: 1.5 for complete recombination). Taking into account the uncertainty of measurement concerning this value this is still in accordance with our assumption.

The degree of polymerization (DOP) from the ¹H-HNMR was plotted against the results from the SEC measurements (*DOP(SEC)*^a-column in Table 1) with a polystyrene standard. Those results show a very good linear dependency. The regression for the DOP(SEC) (see Table 1) fits well with the corresponding plot for the DOP(¹H-NMR)-data, too. So a correction factor based on these regression data was introduced as an approach, to evaluate the correlation between DOP values from ¹H-NMR and SEC (PS-standard) measurements.

Table 1 contains the results for our polymers supporting that for not too small degrees of polymerization the Mark-Houwink correction does work confidently.

Figure 2 shows the DSC results for three different d₀-PAN homopolymers. These measurements were done under an inert argon atmosphere with a heating rate of 20 K/min up to 450 K. From Figure 1 it is obvious, that the molecular weight influences the reaction enthalpy and the peak temperatures of the stabilization processes, since this was the only parameter varied in this series. Furthermore for polymers with a lower averaged molecular weight (but comparable molecular weight distribution), i.e. polymers with shorter chains, the DSC curve widens and the reaction enthalpy ΔH_{Rct} rises respectively. (Table 1).

Polymer	Acrylonitrile (ml)	DOP (SEC) ^a	DOP (SEC _{corr}) ^b	DOP (¹ H-NMR) ^c	DOP (Mark-Houwink) ^d	T _(Peak) (°C)	ΔH_{Rct} (J/g)
2.0 d ₀ -PAN	2	840	376	350	367	297	436
1.5 d ₀ -PAN	1.5	642	288	306	290	307	515
0.2 d ₀ -PAN	0.2	192	86	60	101	309	524
2.0 d ₁ -PAN	2	815	366	360	345	313	412
2.0 d ₃ -PAN	2	1016	456	-	434	322	380

Table 1: Overview of the examined polymers and their experimental results, DOP^a: SEC results with PS calibration, ^b: DOP(SEC) values corrected with the slope from the regression DOP(NMR) vs. DOP(SEC): $y=0,4485x$, ^c: results from ¹H-NMR signal integrals, ^d: SEC values corrected with Mark-Houwink equation according to literature^{12,13}

We conclude from our findings that the lower the degree of polymerization becomes the less auto-catalytic becomes the thermally driven stabilization process (broadness and onset of the DSC signal). This would in principle be in accordance with a dominant intra-chain domino-like propagation step (such as the frequently proposed intramolecular ladder-structure cyclization).

Figure 2: DSC-thermogram for d₀-PANs (blue) 2.0, (green) 1.5 and (red) 0.2

The degree of polymerization as well as the molecular weight distribution has not been taken into account as an important parameter for the stabilization process by now to our knowledge. With our results we would like to sensitize for the fact that it does decisively influence this step. We also have already found that this influence is even more drastic for the dioxygen-dependent reaction pathway which will be discussed in a separate paper.

3.2 Influence of addition of radical initiator

The conclusion that the thermally driven stabilization step is a radically initiated process was founded on the observation that when DPPH (Figure 3) was added to the system an inhibition of the reaction was observed. However, several aspects about this experiment must be considered critical; above all the fact that DPPH is not stable at the temperatures of stabilization (decomposition at 127-129°C).

We thus thought of an alternative experiment and, since no radical inhibitors that would be stable at 290°C are known, we came up with the idea to use a complementary strategy in adding a radical initiator that generates radicals at such high temperatures. We found a candidate suitable for this purpose in Perkadox 30 (provided to us by AkzoNobel Polymer Chemistry, Netherlands; Figure 3), which possesses a half life time of 0.1 h at 284°C.

Our expectation was, that if a radical process is involved in the stabilization then addition of Perkadox 30 should influence this process (either inhibit it by recombination with radicals or accelerate it by providing initiating radicals).

As polyacrylonitrile compound a d₃-PAN homopolymer (2.0 ml d₃-AN used in the procedure described above) was chosen, since its stabilization onset temperature of 309 °C for the pure polymer fits to the temperature range, in which Perkadox 30 (melting point about 110 °C) is expected to increase the radical concentration. The results for these measurements are shown in Figure 4.

Three different powder mixtures have been prepared from the corresponding d₃-PAN and Perkadox 30, which have been mortared and mixed with the PAN mechanically. This procedure is in accordance with the practice of Kim et al. . As it can be seen from the thermograms, the PAN/Perkadox 30 mixtures with different amounts of radical initiator added, do not vary in the position of their peak temperatures. This result disagrees with the radical inhibitor experiments from Kim et al. and suggests,

that the reaction mechanism for the thermal stabilization process under inert conditions cannot rely predominantly on a radical mechanism.

Figure 3: (left): 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), radical inhibitor
(right) 2,3-Dimethyl-2,3-diphenylbutane (Perkadox 30), radical initiator

Figure 4: DSC-thermograms for Perkadox 30-2.0 d₃-PAN mixtures, (darkblue): Perkadox 30, (red): pure 2.0 d₃-PAN, (green): 10% Perkadox 30, (lightblue): 50% Perkadox 30, (black): 66% Perkadox 30

3.3 Examinations concerning intermolecular processes via deuterium-labelled PAN mixtures

In some publications interchain-crosslinking has been taken into account as a side-reaction at least as a discussed possibility¹⁴. Efforts to prove this type of reaction or even to quantify its contribution are extremely rare, though. In general, the intramolecular cyclization reaction dominates the discussion of the stabilization step.

We thought it should be very informative to get insight into this reaction type by examining defined mixtures of differently labelled PAN samples. Because of isotopic effects the signals for d₀-

PAN, d₁-PAN and d₃-PAN show up at distinctively increased temperature ranges, respectively. DSC measurement on pure samples of d₁-, d₂- and d₃-PAN has been done before.¹⁵

Thus, if the stabilization happens to be an intrachain-dominated process, in a mixture of compounds the two signals should show up strictly additively, while if the dominance is by interchain reaction a coupling of the two separated processes should be detectable by one single new signal in between the two pure signals. Figure 5 compares the DSC thermograms for the pure compounds and 50/50 mixtures of them. It can clearly be concluded that a decisive coupling between the chains exists. This is more pronounced with the d₃-PAN, in which case the complete stabilization is dominated by the d₃-PAN, supporting that all three protons –in particular also the CH₂-group– of the repeat unit are involved in the interchain coupling.

Figure 5: DSC-thermograms of 50/50 mechanically prepared mixtures (red) and the corresponding pure PAN (black) samples, i) d₀/d₁ (639 J/g), ii) d₀/d₃ (596 J/g), iii) d₁/d₃ (508 J/g) ;
a) 2.0 d₀-PAN (422 J/g), b) 2.0 d₁-PAN (547 J/g), c) 2.0 d₃-PAN (320 J/g)

3.4 Examinations concerning a possible Ziegler-Thorpe-type reaction contribution

Besides the radical pathway a non-radical channel via Ziegler-Thorpe-type reaction is discussed in several papers, although the evidence for the occurrence of this reaction remains weak and indirect. We thought it should be possible to contribute to this question by examining the smallest defined molecule that could show this kind of reaction, namely the trimer 2,4,6-triscyanoheptane.

2,4,6-Triscyanoheptane was synthesized via a double Michael-addition of methacrylonitrile to *t*-butylcyanoacetate, followed by the removal of the ester via pyrolysis (Figure 6).

The trimer is a white solid with a melting point of 50°C, which was fully characterized by means of ¹H, ¹³C and IR spectroscopy as well as elemental analysis.

When a DSC measurement is performed with this compound in a sealed tube (the boiling point is not high enough for an open measurement) up to temperatures of 320°C, no exothermic peak is found in the thermogram and after cooling to room temperature the starting compound is re-isolated without chemical changes being detectable by IR or ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

Figure 6: Synthesis of 2,4,6-triscyanoheptane i) NaH, Toluene, 85 °C, 48h, ii) Argon and dynamic vacuum, RT to 190 °C (15 min)

Figure 7: Results of LDA- and thermal treatments towards 2,4,6-triscyanoheptane

When on the other hand the trimer is treated with LDA under the usual conditions of a classical Ziegler-Thorpe reaction a quantitative cyclization occurs only under rearrangement of one of the methyl groups (Figure 7). From these findings we must conclude that a Ziegler-Thorpe-type reaction is not very likely to occur during the stabilization process of PAN homopolymer.

4. Conclusions

Our most important conclusions are as follows:

- The degree of polymerization and the molecular weight distribution are decisive parameters for the stabilization step and should be taken into account in future examinations.
- The stabilization step is not predominantly ruled by a radical process.
- Intermolecular cross-linking decisively determines the reactions during the stabilization where all three hydrogens of the repeat unit seem to be involved in this process.
- A Ziegler-Thorpe-type reaction can be ruled out with high probability as a decisive elementary reaction during the stabilization process.

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